

Outstanding Student Attitudes And Feelings Towards Volunteering: Comparative Research Among Students At The Arabic Academic College For Education In Israel And Students At Other Colleges In Israel

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: June 03,2025</p> <p>Accepted: September 08 ,2025</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Asymmetrical Structure, Code-Switching, Content Morphemes, System Morphemes, Matrix Language Frame Model, Urdu-English Codeswitching</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17080549</p>	<p><i>Codeswitching in the context of single or multiple conversations has been a myth for language experts. Matrix language framework (MLF) model proposed by Myers Scotton (1993) has become very popular for the analysis of language pairs, and is influential in determining matrix language in different language pairs. The aim of this study is to identify matrix and embedded language in Urdu-English data sets of health and science theme. MLF model is applied to an original article on Covid-19. Data sets include language pairs from a published article on the nature of coronavirus. A qualitative design was followed to arrange data sets, language pairs were identified, transcribed and coded carefully according to the Canonical Trilinear Representation. Three layers of data with the first layer of roman Urdu, the second layer of gloss and the third layer of English translation were further analyzed syntactically and morphosyntactically to show how they grammatically occur in the bilingual complementiser phrases. The findings of this study reveal that code-switching was permissible even when it led to structural asymmetry. English insertions received different Urdu markers of gender and number wherever required. Urdu adjectives played a significant role in realizing nouns. Some data sets allowed English insertions without Urdu markers. Moreover, the data supported matrix language frame, morpheme order principle and system morpheme principle and no counter example appeared against MLF model. Thus, the present study is a significant contribution in the related area.</i></p>

Introduction

Volunteering exposes someone to many experiences that are related to one's career, increases one's self worth, reduces negative behaviors, strengthens social ties, increases positive life practices, as well as enhances emotional resilience, namely the ability to control, evaluate, express and use emotions to solve problems while increasing understanding on various issues, conflicts and problems faced by the group assisted, especially those who are involved in negative activities (Chong, A. M., 2013).

Someone who is involved in volunteering is a person with social awareness, fighting spirit, universal love and willingness to make sacrifices for the welfare of others (Forbes, K., Zampelli, E. 2014). This social encouragement can be divided into four aspects, namely encouragement from peers, family, the local community and school community. All these encouragements indirectly influence and shape a person's behavior and drive them towards participation in volunteer work. The constant improvement of the social requirements for the quality of talents demands that the social practice be recognized as fundamental in refining student's intellectual capacity and their ability to make appropriate adjustments in an organization and apply their knowledge in the future in terms of academic or real life situations (Maki, Dwyer, Snyder, 2016, Al Shehhi and Azam, 2019a , Tham et al., 2017). Hence, the role of voluntary community service cannot be over emphasized (Dong, 2017).

In recent time, volunteering activities among the youth have been gaining prominence in most developed countries. Jigssa et al. (2018) noted that volunteers feel motivated to carry out task when it affords them prospect for career development even when it does not involve financial benefits at the present. According to Liket & Maas (2015), for organizations to attract more volunteers, the challenges that confronts the volunteers needs to be spotted out and solved. Several factors – both internal and external influences social volunteering activities.

Literature Review

Studies have shown that volunteering services improves the standard of living of the recipient community and progress the civilization of the human society. A person who gets involved in volunteer work is someone who

has social awareness, is highly spirited, loves the world in general and is willing to make sacrifices for others' welfare (Tajul A., Nadirah., A. 2013)

According to Kim, Park, Kim and Kim (2019), in most cases, people who have the intention to be involved in volunteering activities are motivated by intrinsic reward, such as having a pleasure feeling fostered by doing a good job and a sense of doing something that brings benefit to the society.

A recent of volunteering amongst students in tertiary institutions was highlighted by Handy et al. (2010) as career development and resume building form of volunteering, which describes volunteering to build CV.

Volunteering service is a good means for college students to develop their individual and moral cultivation. Chen (2020), acknowledged that, the basis for volunteering is obtained from the moral conscience of the volunteer, and volunteering is a pragmatic demonstration of the desire for building moral cultivation in the individual student.

It is also believed that, people who love to involve in volunteering work will develop a more positive behavior and healthier outlook (Sallam, Safizal& Osman, 2015). This is because, volunteers tend to perceive themselves as optimistic about their future as they feel empowered to assist and improve their community and have that burning motivation to help others who are in need., According to Wery and Thomson (2013), there are two (2) main classification of motivational strategies which are intrinsic and extrinsic motivation.

The general consensus is that the prosocial actions of volunteers offer numerous benefits not only to communities but also to volunteers themselves (Snyder, Omoto, & Dwyer, 2016). While we are not saying that volunteering has no costs or downsides or that all such activities are worth promoting (Clary& Snyder, 2002), on balance, bringing people together in ways that enhance and improve the lives of community members has been shown to be a good thing

Methodology

Research population

The following tables display data about the research population.

1. Distribution of students by gender

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Male	25	25	25	25
Female	75	75	75	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

2. Distribution of students by sector:

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Jewish	46	46	46	46
Arab	54	54	54	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

2. Distribution of students in accordance with the educational institution they are enrolled at

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
The Arabic College	28	28	28	28
Gordon College	10	10	10	38
David Yellin College	13	13	13	51
Givat Washington College	12	12	12	63
Al-Qasemi College	12	12	12	75
Moreshet	13	13	13	88
Beit Berl College	12	12	12	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

In short words, the targeted population includes students enrolled in outstanding tracks in seven colleges, three of which serve the Arab sector (The Arabic College, Al-Qasemi College and Beit Berl) and four of which serve the Jewish sector (Gordon College, David Yellin College, and Moreshet). 25% of these students are males and 75% are female, 54% are from the Arab sector and 46% are from the Jewish sector.

Research Tools & Sample

The two scales have been developed by Szold Institute, The first scale includes 34 items. It collects data on the motives of volunteering. The second scale involves 9 items, The researchers used quantitative research methods. Data was collected from 100 students who were selected through the purposive sampling technique.

Research questions

1. How can the volunteer activities help outstanding students at the Arab College for Education – Haifa, in their view, compared to the other students participating in this research?
2. Are there clear differences between outstanding students at the Arab College for Education – Haifa and students at the other colleges in terms of their feelings toward volunteer activities, the reasons for their volunteering, and how they perceive volunteering will help them in the future?

Results

As noted above, the research aim was to try an answer four questions. Below we present the findings, in the order of the research questions.

1. How can the volunteer activities help outstanding students at the Arab College for Education – Haifa, in their view, compared to the other group of students participating in this research?

To answer this question, means and standard deviation were calculated for the other group of students' answers and for the Arabic College students, in particular, for the ten statements comprising this section. Table 1 present the means of these statements for the two populations.

Table 1: Students' answers regarding the future benefit of their volunteering

No.	Statement	Other Group Mean	S.D.	Arabic College Mean	S.D
1.	An opportunity to acquire professional experience in a new field	3.8	1.2	4.4	0.9
2.	An opportunity to use the experience acquired in a paid job	3.5	1.2	4.3	0.7
3.	The possibility of getting a paid job in the organization where I am volunteering	2.6	1.5	3.6	1.6
4.	An opportunity to acquire new knowledge & skills to implement at work	3.9	1.1	4.5	0.6
5.	An opportunity to strengthen my knowledge & skills in the field where I work	3.6	1.2	4.3	0.8
6.	An opportunity to get a recommendation for other work	3.0	1.3	3.7	1.3
7.	An opportunity to check whether a field that is close to the one where I volunteer suits me	4.2	1.0	4.6	0.7
8.	An opportunity to meet people that will help me in my career	3.6	1.3	4.4	0.7

No.	Statement	Other Group Mean	S.D.	Arabic College Mean	S.D
9.	An opportunity to be valued at my workplace because I volunteer	3.0	1.4	4.0	1.1

Looking at the above findings, we can say that the Arabic College students feel, more than the other group of students, that their volunteering helps them, in all the areas presented in this section of the questionnaire, with no exceptions.

From the findings, we see that there are differences between the answers of the other group of students and the Arabic College students regarding the future benefits from their volunteering. Thus, for example, the other group of students does not believe that volunteering may help enrich them, which will contribute to them as individuals and employees (4.2), as much as the Arabic College students do (4.6), and the other group of students views volunteering less as an opportunity to acquire professional experience in a new field (3.8) than the Arabic College students (4.4).

The most prominent data are the answers for the last two statements. The perception that volunteering will help them meet people that can advance their careers is more widespread among the Arabic College students than among the other group of students (4.0 vs. 3.0, respectively), as is the perception that it will increase the esteem they will receive in their future workplace (4.3 vs. 3.2, respectively).

2. Are there clear differences between outstanding students at the Arab College for Education – Haifa and students at other colleges in terms of their feelings toward volunteer activities, the reasons for their volunteering, and how this volunteering will help them in the future?

To answer this question, we used the independent samples t test to compare the averages of the answers given by the Arabic College students and the rest of the students who participated in the research, for each of the ten statements included in the section on feelings, the 17 questions relating to reasons for volunteering and the ten questions related to possible future benefits for students because they volunteer.

Table 4: Comparison of the means of the answers regarding feelings about volunteering among Arabic College students and the rest of the students participating in the research, according to an independent samples t test.

Table 2: Means of students' answers to the question about their feelings regarding volunteering

No.	Statement	Other Group Mean	Other Group SD	Arabic College Mean	Arabic College SD
1.	I am interested in what I am doing as a volunteer.	4.3	0.8	4.6	0.7
2.	I have the opportunity to express the range of my skills.	4.1	0.8	4.3	0.6
3.	There is a good social atmosphere where I volunteer.	4.6	0.9	4.4	1.0
4.	I have the opportunity to demonstrate my values while volunteering.	4.3	0.7	4.3	0.7
5.	I have independence to make decisions where I volunteer.	4.0	1.0	4.0	0.9
6.	I am appreciated by my superiors where I volunteer.	4.1	1.0	4.2	1.0
7.	The activity times are convenient for me.	3.8	1.1	3.7	1.0
8.	I am satisfied with my volunteering achievements thus far.	4.2	0.8	4.5	0.8
9.	Sometimes, the volunteering is a burden for me.	3.3	1.0	3.3	1.1
10.	I am considering continuing my present volunteering for a long time.	3.1	1.1	3.3	0.8
11.	I am forced to give up important things because of my volunteer work.	3.0	1.2	3.2	1.1
12.	Volunteering gives me a lot of satisfaction.	4.2	0.9	3.9	0.9
13.	In the future, I will prefer to volunteer in different areas.	3.0	1.3	3.0	1.5
14.	In general, volunteering is an activity that I look forward to happily.	3.7	1.0	3.7	1.1

No.	Statement	Other Group Mean	Other Group SD	Arabic College Mean	Arabic College SD
15.	I have a strong sense of belonging where I volunteer.	3.9	1.1	3.9	0.9
16.	I considered or am considering job retraining.	2.4	1.4	2.6	1.5
17.	I am involved in the area that suits me and my skills the best.	3/9	0.8	4.3	0.8

From the above findings, we can say that for most statements in this section (except for two statements) relating to the outstanding students' feelings regarding their volunteering, no statistically significant differences were found. The implication is that there is a high degree of similarity between the Arabic College students and the other students in the excellence tracks of the other colleges who participated in this research, in terms of their feelings.

Regarding two statements differences were found. For the statement "Volunteering gives me a lot of satisfaction", the findings indicate that the Arabic College students are not finding enough satisfaction (3.9) compared to the outstanding students in the other college (4.2). Regarding the statement "I am involved in the area that suits me and my skills best", the opposite is seen: the Arabic College outstanding students tend to view their volunteering activities as suited to their skills (4.3) whereas the students in the other colleges do not (3.9).

Table 3: Comparison of the means of the answers regarding reasons for volunteering among Arabic College students and the rest of the students participating in the research, according to an independent samples t test

No.	Statement	Other Group Mean	Other Group SD	Arabic College Mean	Arabic College SD
1.	It's a commandment.	4.0	1.2	3.9	0.9
2.	I identify with the objectives of the track & the project in which I volunteer.	4.3	0.8	4.2	0.8
3.	If I don't volunteer, there won't be anybody to do the work I do.	2.9	1.3	2.9	1.3
4.	I have nothing better to do with my time.	2.1	1.3	2.4	1.1
5.	I felt lonely.	1.6	0.9	1.8	1.0
6.	I have free time.	1.9	1.1	2.4	1.1
7.	I wanted to get practical experience before getting a paying job.	2.6	1.4	3.3	1.4
8.	I wanted to broaden my horizons.	3.5	1.3	4.1	1.1
9.	It's considered prestigious to be part of the organization or project where I volunteer.	3.1	1.5	4.4	0.6
10.	Volunteering to help others makes me feel better about myself.	4.1	0.7	4.3	0.6
11.	Volunteering provides me with a challenging activity.	3.8	1.1	4.3	0.7
12.	Most of the people closest to me volunteer.	2.5	1.2	2.9	1.2
13.	Helping people in need enhances my approach to my life.	4.0	1.0	4.2	0.9
14.	Volunteering creates a better society.	4.5	0.7	4.4	0.7
15.	The outstanding student track coordinator expects me to volunteer.	4.2	1.0	4.5	0.8
16.	Volunteering is an opportunity to repair social ills.	4.0	0.9	4.3	0.6
17.	Volunteering is an opportunity to develop social contacts.	4.1	1.1	4.4	0.8
18.	This is an opportunity to work with people from different age groups.	4.3	0.9	4.5	0.6
19.	Volunteering constitutes an opportunity to do something worthwhile.	3.8	1.1	4.4	0.7
20.	Volunteering is an opportunity to repay society for my good fortune.	1.8	1.0	3.6	1.1

No.	Statement	Other Group Mean	Other Group SD	Arabic College Mean	Arabic College SD
21.	A relative or friend received this service or a similar service.	2.2	1.5	1.7	0.8
22.	If I don't volunteer, maybe I won't be promoted at work.	2.7	1.6	2.8	1.5
23.	If I don't volunteer, I'll be an exception at the college and in my track.	2.9	1.4	3.3	1.3
24.	I'm expected to volunteer in order to serve as an example to those below me in the track.	2.2	1.2	3.5	1.2
25.	Volunteering compensates for the lack of satisfaction from doing academic assignments in the college.	3.1	1.3	2.3	1.2
26.	I have experience in providing the same sort of services.	3.9	1.1	3.5	1.2
27.	It's easy for me to identify with the population with whom I am volunteering.	3.5	1.1	4.0	1.0
28.	Volunteering is something different in my weekly activities.	2.4	1.5	3.7	0.9
29.	I had earlier contact with the staff of the volunteer organization.	3.8	1.3	3.1	1.6
30.	This is an opportunity to give more help to those who need it for less money.	4.2	0.9	3.9	1.3
31.	It's great educational experience for me.	3.8	1.3	4.4	0.8
32.	My future professional involvement will be along the lines of the field of activities in which I am volunteering.	3.7	1.3	4.3	1.0
33.	I was taught to volunteer.	3.2	1.4	3.8	1.2
34.	My hobby is related to the field of activities in which I am volunteering.	4.0	1.1	3.9	1.1

Looking at the above findings, we can identify not insignificant differences between the Arabic College students and the outstanding students in the other colleges. For 14 of the 34 statements, significant differences were found, as follows:

The Arabic College students want to get practical experience in advance of working for pay more than the outstanding students in the other colleges (3.3 vs. 2.6, respectively), they want to broaden their horizons more (4.1 vs. 3.5, respectively), they feel that volunteering where they do and being part of the organization or project is prestigious (4.4 vs. 3.10, respectively), they believe that volunteering makes them feel better about themselves (4.3 vs. 4.1, respectively), they feel that it provides them with a challenging activity (4.3 vs. 3.3, respectively), they perceive that most people around them volunteer (2.9 vs. 2.5), they believe that it is an opportunity to develop social contacts (4.1 vs. 4.4 respectively), they feel that it is an opportunity to work with people of different ages (4.5 vs. 4.3, respectively), they believe that if they do not volunteer, they will not be promoted at work (2.8 vs. 2.7, respectively), they think that if they do not volunteer, they will be the exceptions in their study track (3.3 vs. 2.9, respectively), they believe that they are expected to set a personal example (3.5 vs. 2.2, respectively), they had previous contact with the staff working at the organization where they are volunteering (3.1 vs. 3.8, respectively), they feel that their future professional career is related to their volunteer activities (4.3 vs. 3.7, respectively), and their hobbies are related to the field in which they are volunteering (4.0 vs. 3.9, respectively).

Table 4: Comparison of the answers of the Arabic College students and the rest of the students participating in the research, regarding how the volunteering will help them in the future, according to the averages

No.	Statement	Average among Arabic College students	Average among the rest of the students	t	Sig. (2-tailed).
1.	An opportunity to acquire professional experience in a new field	4.18	3.57	2.35	0.02

No.	Statement	Average among Arabic College students	Average among the rest of the students	t	Sig. (2-tailed).
2.	An opportunity to use the experience acquired in a paid job	4.29	3.18	5.51	0.00
3.	The possibility of getting a paid job in the organization where I am volunteering	3.59	2.21	4.29	0.00
4.	An opportunity to acquire new knowledge & skills to implement at work	4.48	3.71	4.16	0.00
5.	An opportunity to strengthen my knowledge & skills in the field where I work	4.33	3.27	4.92	0.00
6.	An opportunity to get a recommendation for other work	3.66	2.72	3.22	0.00
7.	An opportunity to check whether a field that is close to the one where I volunteer suits me	4.40	3.24	5.64	0.00
8.	An opportunity to meet people that will help me in my career	4.03	2.53	5.30	0.00
9.	An opportunity to be valued at my workplace because I volunteer	4.33	2.73	6.63	0.00

Looking at the above findings, we can say that there are significant differences between the Arabic College students and the outstanding students in the other colleges related to the statements regarding future professional benefits from volunteering.

The Arabic College students feel that their volunteer activities give them an opportunity to acquire professional experience in a new field, to express the experience they acquired in their paid job in their volunteer work, to get a job later on in the organization where they are volunteering, to acquire new knowledge and skills, to strengthen knowledge and skills in the field where they work, and to be valued at their future workplace because of their volunteering. The outstanding students from the Arabic College agree more to a significant degree with all the above statements than the students in the excellence tracks in the other colleges.

Discussion & Conclusions

This evaluation research aimed to examine the attitudes of outstanding students toward the volunteer activities that they are required to participate in as a condition for joining the excellence track. One of the principles underpinning the excellence program is that outstanding students contribute to the community and not just receive something from it (Lieberman, 2001). In this research we sought to reveal the attitudes of the Arabic College students and compare them to those of outstanding students from six other colleges – two colleges from the Arabic sector and four colleges from the Jewish sector. In total, 100 outstanding students, 28 of whom were from the Arabic College, studying in the excellence tracks at these colleges participated.

The research focused on three areas related to contribution to the community: (a) students' feelings toward volunteering; (b) the reasons why they are contributing to the community; and (c) the future benefits they expect to get because of their volunteer activities.

Question 1: How can the volunteer activities help outstanding students at the Arab College for Education – Haifa, in their view, compared to the other students participating in this research?

The findings for this question indicate that the Arabic College students see in their volunteer activities, more than the outstanding students from the other colleges, something that may help them in the future.

The Arabic College students, more than the other students, perceive that volunteering enriches them both as individuals and employees. The same is true about acquiring professional experience in a new field, meeting people who may help them in their careers and the desire to be more involved in their future place of work because of the having volunteered.

Question 2: Are there clear differences between outstanding students at the Arab College for Education – Haifa and students at other colleges in terms of their feelings toward volunteer activities, the reasons for their volunteering, and how this volunteering will help them in the future?

No significant differences were found between the Arabic College outstanding students and the other students in terms of their feelings toward the volunteer activities they perform, except in regard to two statements: the Arabic College students feel less satisfied by the volunteer activities than the other students, but nevertheless, they reported that they are involved in the most appropriate field given their skills. This information is very interesting. The Arabic College students ascribe great importance to their volunteer activities being congruent

with their skills and are very interested in them but are not satisfied by them relative to the other students. One possible explanation for this finding may be that these students aspire to volunteer more or invest more in their volunteering, and most likely are not finding someone to talk to about this.

In the section that examined the reasons for volunteering, 14 significant differences between the Arabic College students and the outstanding students from the other colleges were found regarding the following statements: the former want to get more practical experience in advance of getting a better-paid job, they want to broaden their horizons, it is prestigious in their opinion to be part of the organization or project where they are volunteering, volunteering makes them feel better about themselves, it gives them something challenging to do, they feel that most people around them volunteer, it is an opportunity to develop social contacts, it is an opportunity to work with groups of people of different ages, they feel that if they did not volunteer, they would not be promoted at work and would be the exceptions in their study track, they are expected to serve as an example, they had earlier contact with the staff at the organization where they volunteer, their future professional job is related to the field where they are volunteering and their hobby is related to the field in which they are volunteering. Regarding the remainder of statements, no significant differences were found.

In terms of perceiving their volunteer activities as helping them in the future, significant differences were found between the Arabic College students and the outstanding students from the other colleges in all the statements related to future professional benefits from volunteering. The former students feel that the volunteer activities give them the opportunity to acquire experience in a new field, to use their experience from their paid place of work, to get a job in the future in the organization where they volunteer, to acquire new knowledge and skills, to strengthen their knowledge and skills in the field where they work, to get recommendations for work, to be enriched, to check whether the field in which they are volunteering suits them, to get to know people who may help their career and to be valued at their future place of work because they volunteered. With each of the above statements, the Arabic College outstanding students agreed to a significant degree more than the students studying in the excellence tracks of the other colleges.

Recommendations

The authors recommend to expand the study to other cultures and make compare in order to determine the to which extent the volunteering is important among students over the investigated cultures, we recommend also to the stakeholders to encourage students to volunteer as partial from f there studying fulfilment.

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